

ACOUSTIC EMISSION IN LAMINATED BEAMS DUE TO FIBER FRACTURES

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SUMMARY: A model for excitation and propagation of waves resulting from fiber fracture in laminated beams is presented. The fiber fracture was described as a time dependent displacement discontinuity and wave propagation was modeled by a higher order beam theory. The equations of motion defined by the beam model were then formally solved by employing integral transforms. Asymptotically valid solutions were subsequently found using residue calculus and the stationary phase method. In particular displacement velocities at different points in a $[90/0_2/90]$ beam with a width to thickness ratio of 10 is presented. Based on the results it is concluded that fiber fracture excites several modes of vibration in the specimen, also a criterion for validity range, in frequency, of beam models is suggested.

KEYWORDS: wave propagation, fiber fracture, acoustic emission, laminated beams

INTRODUCTION

The properties of damaged composite materials is often studied experimentally through uniaxial testing of thin beam-like specimens. A damage state which often precedes final specimen failure is fracture of individual fibers. A fracturing fiber will release stress waves which can be detected and recorded on the surface of the specimen using wide-band transducers [1]. In principle the recorded stress waves can be used to extract information about the location, duration of the fracture event and other parameters. As a first step it is valuable to model the fiber fracture and wave propagation in the specimen.

A fiber fracture can be viewed as a time-dependent displacement discontinuity across the fracture surfaces. In [2] it was shown how such a discontinuity can be translated to an equivalent body force. Furthermore, since fiber fracture is highly localized, on the specimen level, it is possible to collect the geometry of the fracture and the body force in a so-called moment tensor, see for example [3].

Wave propagation in the specimen is complicated by the large number of reflections from the boundaries, or looking at a larger scale, by the fact that wave propagation in the laminated beam is dispersive. Waveguides have been studied extensively using different methods, fairly recent surveys of the literature may be found in the introductions of [4] and [5]. In this work a higher order beam theory is used to model wave propagation. The approximate equations of motion for the beam are derived from an assumed displacement field using Hamilton's principle. They are then solved using Fourier transforms and approximate inversion using residue calculus and the stationary phase method.

SOURCE MODEL

A laminated beam with symmetric lay-up and a Cartesian coordinate system according to Fig.

1 was considered. The laminate is made of transversely isotropic plies.

Fig. 1: Geometry of laminated beam and coordinate system

It is infinite in the 1-direction and bounded by free surfaces at $x_2 = \pm b$ and $x_3 = \pm h$. In modeling the fiber fracture, it is for simplicity assumed that it occurs in a 0° -ply. The location of the fiber fracture was set to $x_1 = 0$, $x_2 = b_f$ and $x_3 = h_f$, and the volume force was expressed with the help of a moment tensor as

$$f_i = -M_{ij}(t) \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} [\delta(x_1) \delta(x_2 - b_f) \delta(x_3 - h_f)], \quad (1)$$

where the moment tensor, M_{ij} , is given by

$$M_{ij}(t) = \bar{u}^{\text{stat}} J_f(t) r^2 \pi C_{ij11}^f. \quad (2)$$

Here \bar{u}^{stat} is the average separation between the broken fiber ends under static loading, C_{ijkl}^f the stiffness tensor of the fiber and r the radius of the fiber. The time dependence was assumed to have the form

$$J_f(t) = \begin{cases} t/\tau & 0 < t < \tau \\ 1 & \tau < t \end{cases}. \quad (3)$$

This means that the average separation increases linearly during a time period of length τ to the value it would have in the static case.

The value of \bar{u}^{stat} can be estimated in different ways. A simple estimate due to Cox was used, see [7]. Using Cox's model and letting the fiber length approach infinity, the separation of the fiber ends becomes

$$\bar{u}^{\text{stat}} = \bar{\epsilon}_1 r \sqrt{\frac{E_f \ln(1/V_f)}{G_m}}, \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\epsilon}_1$ is the strain in the 1-direction of the ply, r the radius of the fiber, E_f the elastic modulus of the fiber, V_f the fiber volume fraction and G_m the shear modulus of the matrix material.

LAMINATED BEAM MODELS

Consider a laminated beam loaded by volume forces f_i according to Eqn 1. In order to derive a beam model, *i. e.* to homogenize over the 2- and 3-directions, the displacements, u_i , were expressed in terms of Legendre polynomials,

$$u_i(x_j, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} P_n\left(\frac{x_2}{b}\right) P_m\left(\frac{x_3}{h}\right) u_i^{(n,m)}(x_1, t), \quad (5)$$

where P_n is the Legendre polynomial of degree n . The next step is to truncate the series and use Hamilton's principle to generate equations of motion. This technique has been used earlier, see for example [7-8]. For symmetric laminates only certain combinations of m and n appear together because the motion will be symmetric or antisymmetric with respect to the 2- and 3-axes. Thus, there are four basic types of wave propagation. Extensional wave propagation is symmetric with respect to both the 2- and 3-axes. Bending around the 2-axis is antisymmetric with respect to that axis and symmetric with respect to the 3-axis, and vice-versa for bending around the 3-axis. Twisting, finally, is antisymmetric with respect to both axes. Twisting motion was not treated because twisting is excited through warping of the cross-section only, and hence the motion due to twisting will probably be small.

In truncation of the series, Eqn 5, use was also made of the fact that the beams considered were thin, that is the width $2b$ was much larger than the thickness $2h$. In thin beams the stress σ_{33} will be small, at least for long wavelengths, and therefore terms in the series that have to do with lateral contraction in the 3-direction were omitted. Instead it was assumed that the material in the beam is under at state of plane stress. Hence ply p followed the constitutive relation

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11}^p \\ \sigma_{22}^p \\ \sigma_{23}^p \\ \sigma_{13}^p \\ \sigma_{12}^p \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c_{11}^p & c_{12}^p & 0 & 0 & c_{16}^p \\ c_{12}^p & c_{22}^p & 0 & 0 & c_{26}^p \\ 0 & 0 & c_{44}^p & c_{45}^p & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & c_{45}^p & c_{55}^p & 0 \\ c_{16}^p & c_{26}^p & 0 & 0 & c_{66}^p \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11}^p \\ \varepsilon_{22}^p \\ \varepsilon_{23}^p \\ \varepsilon_{13}^p \\ \varepsilon_{12}^p \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

where c_{ij}^p are the ply plane stress stiffnesses .

Finite element computations were performed using the method in [9] and the resulting mode forms were used as a guide in truncation. Truncation was done so that the two lowest modes of vibration would be modeled.

Extensional motion (E)

Terms containing $u_1^{(0,0)}$, $u_1^{(2,0)}$ and $u_2^{(1,0)}$ were kept. The equations of motion resulting from Hamilton's principle are

$$\begin{aligned} 2A_{11} b u_{1,1}^{(0,0)} + 2\eta A_{12} u_{2,1}^{(1,0)} + F_1^{(0,0)} &= 2Pb\ddot{u}_1^{(0,0)} \\ -2\eta A_{12} u_{1,1}^{(0,0)} + \frac{2}{3} A_{66} b u_{2,1}^{(1,0)} - 2\eta^2 A_{22} b^{-1} u_2^{(1,0)} + 2A_{66} u_{1,1}^{(2,0)} + F_2^{(1,0)} &= \frac{2}{3} P b \ddot{u}_2^{(1,0)} \quad (7) \\ -2A_{66} u_{2,1}^{(1,0)} + \frac{2}{5} A_{11} b u_{1,1}^{(2,0)} - 6A_{66} b^{-1} u_1^{(2,0)} + F_1^{(2,0)} &= \frac{2}{5} P b \ddot{u}_1^{(2,0)} \end{aligned}$$

where the subscript ,1 and dot denotes derivation with respect to x_1 and time respectively. The factor η is a correction factor introduced in order to get a closer fit between the dispersion curves from finite elements and the present beam theory. The quantities A_{ij} , P and $F_i^{(m,n)}$ are defined using the density $\rho(x_3)$, the stiffness $c_{ij}(x_3)$ and volume forces f_i as

$$[A_{ij}, D_{ij}] = \int_{-h}^h c_{ij}(x_3)[1, x_3^2] dx_3, \quad (8)$$

$$[P, I] = \int_{-h}^h \rho(x_3)[1, x_3^2] dx_3 \quad (9)$$

(the quantity I will be used later) and

$$F_i^{(n,m)}(x_1, t) = \int_{-h-b}^h \int_{-b}^b f_i(x_j, t) P_n\left(\frac{x_2}{b}\right) P_m\left(\frac{x_3}{h}\right) dx_2 dx_3. \quad (10)$$

Bending around the 2-axis (B2)

In this case terms containing $u_1^{(0,1)}$, $u_1^{(2,1)}$, $u_2^{(1,1)}$, $u_3^{(0,0)}$ and $u_3^{(2,0)}$ were kept. The resulting equations of motion are

$$\begin{aligned} 2D_{11} \frac{b}{h^2} u_{1,11}^{(0,1)} - 2A_{55} \frac{b}{h^2} u_1^{(0,1)} - 2A_{55} \frac{b}{h} u_{3,1}^{(0,0)} + 2 \frac{\mu D_{12}}{h^2} u_{2,1}^{(1,1)} + F_1^{(0,1)} &= 2I \frac{b}{h^2} \ddot{u}_1^{(0,1)} \\ 2A_{55} \frac{b}{h} u_{1,1}^{(0,1)} + 2A_{55} b u_{3,11}^{(0,0)} + F_3^{(0,0)} &= 2P b \ddot{u}_3^{(0,0)} \\ -2 \frac{\mu D_{12}}{h^2} u_{1,1}^{(0,1)} + \frac{2}{3} D_{66} \frac{b}{h^2} u_{2,11}^{(1,1)} - \left(\frac{2\mu^2 D_{22}}{b h^2} + \frac{2A_{44} b}{3 h^2} \right) u_2^{(1,1)} + 2 \frac{D_{66}}{h^2} u_{1,1}^{(2,1)} - 2 \frac{A_{44}}{h} u_3^{(2,0)} + F_2^{(1,1)} &= \frac{2I b}{3 h^2} \ddot{u}_2^{(1,1)} \quad (11) \\ -2 \frac{D_{66}}{h^2} u_{2,1}^{(1,1)} + \frac{2}{5} D_{11} \frac{b}{h^2} u_{1,11}^{(2,1)} - \left(\frac{6D_{66}}{b h^2} + \frac{2A_{55} b}{5 h^2} \right) u_1^{(2,1)} - \frac{2}{5} A_{55} \frac{b}{h} u_{3,1}^{(2,0)} + F_1^{(2,1)} &= \frac{2I b}{5 h^2} \ddot{u}_1^{(2,1)} \\ -2 \frac{A_{44}}{h} u_2^{(1,1)} + \frac{2}{5} A_{55} \frac{b}{h} u_{1,1}^{(2,1)} + \frac{2}{5} A_{55} b u_{3,11}^{(2,0)} - 6 \frac{A_{44}}{b} u_3^{(2,0)} + F_3^{(2,0)} &= \frac{2}{5} P b \ddot{u}_3^{(2,0)} \end{aligned}$$

In this case a correction factor μ was used.

Bending around the 3-axis (B3)

Motion associated with bending around the 3-axis was described by the terms containing $u_1^{(1,0)}$, $u_1^{(3,0)}$, $u_2^{(0,0)}$ and $u_2^{(2,0)}$. The equations of motion are

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2}{3} A_{11} b u_{1,11}^{(1,0)} - 2 \frac{A_{66}}{b} u_1^{(1,0)} - 2 \frac{A_{66}}{b} u_1^{(3,0)} - 2 A_{66} u_{2,1}^{(0,0)} + 2 A_{12} u_{2,1}^{(2,0)} + F_1^{(1,0)} &= \frac{2}{3} P b \ddot{u}_1^{(1,0)} \\ -2 \frac{A_{66}}{b} u_1^{(1,0)} + \frac{2}{7} A_{11} b u_{1,11}^{(3,0)} - 12 \frac{A_{66}}{b} u_1^{(3,0)} - 2 A_{66} u_{2,1}^{(0,0)} - 2 A_{66} u_{2,1}^{(2,0)} + F_1^{(3,0)} &= \frac{2}{7} P b \ddot{u}_1^{(3,0)} \quad (12) \\ 2 A_{66} u_{1,1}^{(1,0)} + 2 A_{66} u_{1,1}^{(3,0)} + 2 A_{66} b u_{2,11}^{(0,0)} + F_2^{(0,0)} &= 2 P b \ddot{u}_2^{(0,0)} \\ -2 A_{12} u_{1,1}^{(1,0)} + 2 A_{66} u_{1,1}^{(3,0)} + \frac{2}{5} A_{66} b u_{2,11}^{(2,0)} - 6 \frac{A_{22}}{b} u_2^{(2,0)} + F_2^{(2,0)} &= \frac{2}{5} P b \ddot{u}_2^{(2,0)} \end{aligned}$$

For this type of motion no correction factors were introduced.

ASYMPTOTIC SOLUTION

The equations of motion, Eqn:s 7, 11 and 12 were solved using the following Fourier transform pairs

$$\hat{g}(\xi, t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(x, t) e^{-i\xi x} dx \quad , \quad g(x, t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{g}(\xi, t) e^{i\xi x} d\xi \quad , \quad (13)$$

$$g^*(x, \omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(x, t) e^{i\omega t} dt \quad , \quad g(x, t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g^*(x, \omega) e^{-i\omega t} d\omega \quad . \quad (14)$$

The subscript 1 is dropped for convenience. The resulting algebraic equations can be summarized using a matrix, \underline{K} , containing the stiffnesses A_{ij} and D_{ij} , a matrix, \underline{M} , containing the inertia factors P and I , the vector \hat{f}^* , which has the transformed generalized beam forces $\hat{F}_i^{*(n,m)}$ as its elements and the vector \hat{u}^* containing the transformed displacements $\hat{u}_i^{*(n,m)}$. The result is

$$[\underline{K}(\xi) - \omega^2 \underline{M}] \hat{u}^* = \hat{f}^*(\xi, \omega) \quad . \quad (15)$$

The homogeneous version of Eqn 15 defines an eigenvalue problem, and since the matrices \underline{K} and \underline{M} are Hermitian, it has p real eigenvalues, ω_n^2 , and generally complex eigenvectors, v_n . The eigenvectors were normalized such that

$$v_n^H \underline{K} v_n = \omega_n^2 \quad , \quad (16)$$

$$v_n^H \underline{M} v_m = \delta_{mn} \quad , \quad (17)$$

where δ_{mn} is Kronecker's delta and the superscript H denotes transpose and complex conjugation. Using Eqn:s 16 and 17 and Eqn 15 the transformed solution \hat{u}^* was written as

$$\hat{u}^*(\xi, \omega) = \sum_{n=1}^p \frac{v_n^H(\xi) \hat{f}^*(\xi, \omega)}{\omega_n^2(\xi) - \omega^2} v_n(\xi) \quad . \quad (18)$$

The inversion of Eqn 18 is done approximately with respect to ξ using contour integration and residue calculus. Only large values of x are considered so the contributions from complex and imaginary poles are neglected. Details regarding this kind of procedure can be found in [10], for example. The resulting expression has to be inverted with respect to ω . For numerical reasons it is better to invert the time-derivative of u^* . An asymptotically valid (*i.e.* large t) inversion of \dot{u}^* is done using the stationary phase method, see for example [11].

EXAMPLE

A symmetric cross-ply ([90/0₂/90]) laminate with ply properties according to Table 1 was considered. The ratio b/h was set to 10. The dispersion curves for the laminate according to Eqn:s 10-12 are shown in Fig. 2. The symbols in the figure are results from finite element computations. The dimensionless frequency $\omega = \sqrt{E_L/\rho}(2b)^{-1}$ is shown as a function of $2\xi b$. The best fit was achieved for $\mu = 0.82$ and $\eta = 0.87$.

Table 1 : Laminate ply properties

E_L (GPa)	E_T (GPa)	ν_{LT}	ν_{TT}	G_{LT} (GPa)	ρ (kg/m ³)
46	18	0.29	0.42	7.9	1930

The finite element computations also showed that the fourth optical mode (not shown) start at 2.6 in the diagram, therefore a maximum dimensionless frequency of 2.5 was used in the inversion.

Fig. 2: Dimensionless frequency against dimensionless wavenumber. Symbols denote finite element results. Solid, dashed and dotted curves denote beam model results for E-, B2- and B3-motion, respectively.

Material properties used for the fiber and matrix are shown in Table 2. The time of fracture τ was set to $2r(\sqrt{E_f/\rho_f})^{-1}$, where the fiber radius r had the typical value $5b \cdot 10^{-4}$. Fracture was assumed to occur at $h_f = h/4$ and $b_f = b/2$, and the strain $\bar{\epsilon}_1$ was set to 2%.

Table 2 : Fiber and matrix properties

E_f (GPa)	ν_f	ρ_f (kg/m ³)	E_m (GPa)	ν_m	ρ_m (kg/m ³)
73	0.22	2492	4.0	0.35	1120

Figs 3, 4 and 5 show the velocities \dot{u}_1 , \dot{u}_2 and \dot{u}_3 respectively of the upper right corner of the beam ($x_2 = b$, $x_3 = h$) at $x_1 = 100b$ as function of time. The labeled arrows in the figures mark the arrival of the different modes. Since plane stress has been used the E- and B3-waves do not contribute to the vertical motion shown in Fig. 5. The figures clearly show that fiber fracture excites several modes of vibration. It should, however, be remembered that this is far away from the source. Closer to the source the specimen will act more like a plate and fewer plate modes will be needed to describe the same frequency range.

CONCLUSIONS

It was found that both the acoustical and the optical modes of all the considered types of wave propagation were excited by the fiber fracture. Also, judging from the comparison of the dispersion relations, the laminated beam model describes the motion in the beam with fair accuracy, at least up to the frequency of the second acoustical mode. This may be used as a criterion for validity of beam models - the model is valid up to the frequency of the lowest optical mode not described by the assumed displacement field.

Fig. 3: Horizontal velocity in the 1-direction due to fiber fracture

Fig. 4: Horizontal velocity in the 2-direction due to fiber fracture

Fig. 5: Vertical velocity due to fiber fracture

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